

Site: TEMPLE Season GS 79-80Area: N. COLONNADE Square R16 Locus Number 4dProgress of Excavation Appears under 4c as mottled grey
sand-gypsum mix - fairly flat 13/12/80 cleaned surface of 4d so that photographedto plan could drawn. // 14/1/80: 4d ^{ALL} Removed, mottled gypsum
vein ran primarily → NE through center of deposit (see plan)Otherwise similar to 4c: brown damp sand, charcoal flecks,
limestone, granite, dolomite, sherdNo Flotation, dry sieving done samples of soil, stone
material before and after sieving Excavated w/ trowel (tip
and scraping) and brushLocus Description "Mottled grey sand gypsum mix" w/ limestone,
some granite frags, fairly flatLocation in Square NE CornerUnder Locus 4c ^{BROWN SAND, STONE}
RUBBLE Over Locus ⑤ BUFF GYPSUMLocus Dimensions ≈ 11 cm thickLevels 7.94 ± - 2-3 cmAnalysis of non-artifactual materials OBJECTS: 1 flint worked point
1 Alabaster frag w
indications finished surface